

MEASURING WALL SHEAR STRESS IN DIRECTION AND MAGNITUDE

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ABSTRACT:

Measuring the wall-shear stress has always been a challenging task. Direct measurements of these forces is expensive and often demands for large space for installation of the sensor. In this paper we present the delta surface hot film sensor (DSHF) that uses three hot-film sensor elements working in CTA mode. Thereby, the shear stress magnitude and direction was detected. The capability of the DSHF sensor to detect fluctuations of the shear-stress vector is also highlighted. Results from three experiments are discussed within the paper. After the calibration the sensor successfully detected the shear stress of a turbulent boundary layer of a flat plate. In the second experiment a critical half diffusor with separated flow was utilized. The flow field was actuated by means of an unsteady working actuator. The forced flow dynamics were also resolved by the DSHF sensor. In the third test the sensor was exposed to a highly three-dimensional flow at a higher Mach number.

1. INTRODUCTION

In boundary-layer theory of the wall shear stress is an important quantity. It is a measure for the energy required to move fluid over a surface. The knowledge of the shear stress can also be useful to detect the boundary layer condition w.r.t. flow separations. Direct measurements of the local shear stress is the ideal method [1]. The size of the sensors often leads to integration problems. The mechanical complexity of conventional shear stress balances lead to high costs of a test setup.

For a general understanding of complex wall-bounded flows the shear stress vector is an important quantity. Therefore, not only the magnitude needs to be known, but also the direction of the local stream line. The direction of the local shear stress vector in complex flow conditions can be determined using oil-paint visualization techniques or tuft visualization [2], [3]. Langston [4] used ink traces to detect local wall-bounded flow directions.

In the presented paper a sensor is introduced which is based on the hot-film technology. The hot-film sensor in general uses the Nusselt-Reynolds

analogy to detect the local shear stress. Therefore, the shear stress can be expressed by a function that depends on the bridge-voltage, $\tau = f(U_{br})$ [5]. This type of sensor was investigated in multiple applications. In [6] hot-films were used to detect local shear stress in laminar and turbulent flows. A correction of the temperature characteristic of the hot-film sensor is also suggested in this work. Hot-films or hot-wires are suitable to detect fluctuations of the shear stress field, as shown in [7]. A hot-wire or hot-film sensor features a characteristic w.r.t. the flow angle, as presented in [8]. This characteristic can be utilized to detect the direction of the local shear stress vector. Therefore, more than one hot-film/hot-wire sensor must be used. McCroskey [9] used two sensor elements to detect all properties of the shear stress vector. A flow angle ranging from $\alpha = \pm 45^\circ$ could be detected. By adding a third sensor element the shear stress vector can be measured in the full range of flow angles ($\alpha = 0^\circ$ to $\alpha = 360^\circ$). This type of sensor was introduced by Dobriloff [10]. It was possible to resolve the shear-stress vector field in the wake of a wall mounted cylinder. This technique was also used to measure the shear-stress distribution on the suction surface of a large scale compressor stator blade [11]. It was shown that the local shear stress vectors could be detected in non-separated flow conditions. Within the current paper, the Delta Surface Hot-Film (DSHF) sensor is introduced. The device is very similar to the ones mentioned above. The geometrical arrangement was adapted to decrease the size of the device. The suggested calibration procedure closely follows the one presented in [10] and [11].

The sensor-design is part of the CleanSky 2 project SKOPA. Within this project a measurement technique is developed that allows to measure local shear stress vectors in magnitude and direction. The global objective is to use the sensor for in-flight experiments and also measure the shear-stress fluctuations. Furthermore, fibre optic pressure sensors are developed that can also be applied in large scale aircraft testing. Both sensor types should feature the robustness to suit in-flight conditions.

Within the current paper results from two different wind tunnels are shown, where dynamic shear-stress vector field have been resolved using the DSHF sensor. In both cases flow separation was

counteracted by means of Active Flow Control (AFC). For AFC fluidic oscillators were utilized. This type of actuators were already successfully applied to complex flows. In [12] it was feasible to reduce the drag of a complex outer wing wind tunnel model at a Reynolds number of $Re = 2 \cdot 10^6$ at a typical take-off Mach number of $Ma = 0.2$.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Results from two different wind tunnel tests are presented within this paper. After calibration the shear stress sensors were placed in a low-speed wind tunnel with regulated flow temperature. In a second experiment the sensors were tested in a highly three dimensional high-speed flow.

Low-speed wind tunnel

The wind-tunnel features a low inflow turbulence level of $Tu = 0.4\%$ and is therefore suitable for boundary layer investigations. Furthermore, a freshwater cooling system is installed to control the temperature of the flow and to ensure a constant Reynolds number during the experiments. The experiments were conducted at a constant inflow speed of $U_\infty = 20$ m/s. A sketch of the wind tunnel facility is shown in Figure 1. For the experiments the test section was equipped with half-diffusor which's diffuser angle α could be varied. The pressure recovery Δc_p of the half diffusor with changing diffuser angles is shown in Figure 2. A linear increase of the pressure recovery is evident until reaching the diffuser angle of $\alpha = 20^\circ$. For

Figure 1: Low-speed wind tunnel and test-body

Figure 2: Normal force coefficient c_n and static pressure coefficient Δc_p for increasing diffuser angle α , [13]

increasing diffuser angles pressure induced flow separation emerges and less pressure recoveries are reached. The test section was equipped with an active flow control (AFC) system. Experiments were conducted using a diffuser angle of $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (flat-plate configuration) and $\alpha = 23^\circ$ (half-diffusor configuration). In case of the flat-plate configuration the measured boundary layer properties should be of the kind of a turbulent boundary layer. When the test section is operated in the half diffusor configuration the strong adverse pressure gradient will lead to local flow separation, which will be counteracted by means of AFC. The extend of the

Figure 3: Detailed setup of the test section

occurring flow separation and the impact of the AFC will be measured by means of delta-surface hot film (DSHF) sensors w.r.t. the local shear stress. Within the experiments eight DSHF sensors were installed on the surface of the test section. All of them downstream the AFC position. The sensors were mounted on a traversable insert to resolve the entire shear-stress field downstream the actuator. A detailed view of the test section and the implemented actuator for AFC is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 5: switching frequency characteristic of the actuator

The actuator consists of a fluidic oscillator that is connected to six outlet orifices. Due to the properties of the device, pulsed fluid jets are produced at each outlet of the device when a minimum amount of supply air mass flow is provided. The actuator was designed to feature a nearly constant switching frequency over a wider range of supply mass-flow rates. Figure 5 indicates the frequency of the pulsed outlet jets w.r.t. the supply mass-flow rate. A minimum mass-flow of $\dot{m} = 1.1$ g/s is needed to force oscillations inside the device. From there on a nearly constant switching frequency of $f = 1450$ Hz is obtained. When the supply mass-flow rate is increased over $\dot{m} = 3.9$ g/s the switching frequency drops to $f = 300$ Hz. In-between $\dot{m} = 3$ g/s and $\dot{m} = 3.9$ g/s an area of hysteresis results. In the presented results the device was operated at $\dot{m} = 4$ g/s ($f = 300$ Hz). Further information on the operating principle of such types of actuator are found in [14] and [15].

sweeping jet actuator

Figure 4: Ramp for high-speed tests and sweeping jet actuator (SJA)

High speed wind tunnel

The high-speed wind tunnel tests were conducted in the transonic wind tunnel at TUB. The Eifel wind tunnel features a rectangular test section of 0.15m x 0.15m. The test section was equipped with a half-diffusor ramp. The key features of the ramp are shown in Figure 4. The diffuser angle was equivalent to the one from the low-speed tests and equaled $\alpha = 23^\circ$. The step height was $h=0.075m$. The experiments were conducted at a inflow Mach number of $Ma = 0.4$. An actuator insert equipped with two sweeping jet actuators (SWJ) is installed. The key geometry of the SWJ is also shown in Figure 4. The SWJ actuator is a self-oscillating device. Compressed air accelerates over the inlet nozzle and enters into the interaction zone. Caused by the Coandă effect, the fluid jet attaches to one side of the attachment walls and streams along the curved surface to the exit nozzle, where the exit jet is formed. A fraction of the fluid enters the feed-back channel and is led back to the interaction zone, where it pushes the attached jet to the opposite attachment wall. Thereby, a sweeping motion of the exit jet is generated. The characteristics of the oscillating jet depends on the internal geometry of the actuator and on the supply pressure ratio. The actuators are located at the natural separation line of the ramp. The blowing angle of the SWJ equalled 30° w.r.t. the surface. Downstream the actuator insert the sensors for the wall-shear stress measurements (DSHF) were installed.

3. THE DSHF SENSOR

For measuring the wall-shear stress magnitude and direction the DSHF sensor was used. The sensor consists of three hot-film elements that are arranged in an angular pattern with an angular shift of $\Delta\omega = 120^\circ$. The DSHF sensor is shown in Figure 6. The hot-film elements are manufactured from nickel. These elements are connected to copper leads with lead wires connected to them. Each hot-film element is driven by a hot-wire bridge circuit, operated in CTA (Constant Temperature Anemometry) mode. The DSHF sensor and the copper leads are manufactured to a flexible polyimide film. The sensor is coated by parylene to increase the robustness of the device.

Figure 6: DSHF (Delta Surface Hot-Film) sensor

Due to the different resistances of every hot-film element, the DSHF sensor demands for a calibration procedure before use. The two experiments (low-speed, and high-speed experiment) demanded for a calibration of the sensors at different wall shear stress ranges. Therefore, two different calibration procedures were applied. These procedures are described in the following sections.

Calibration procedure for low-speed experiments

Here, each sensor was placed in a turbulent reference flow, with a reference system that measured the actual shear stress. The well-known reference flow was a turbulent boundary layer of a flat plate. The reference measurement system was a Preston tube probe. The shear stress was evaluated by utilizing the CPM (Computational Preston tube Method) [16]. The setup of the calibration experiment is shown in Figure 7. Four DSHF sensors were calibrated simultaneously.

Figure 7: DSHF calibration setup

The DSHF sensor inserts were rotated around their axis to calibrate the bridge voltage w.r.t. the local flow angle β . Six different shear stresses were calibrated for each flow angle and sensor. The shear stresses were adjusted by controlling the inflow speed of the calibration wind tunnel. The shear stress, measured by the reference system was converted to the friction coefficient that is defined as $c_f = \tau/q$ (The measured shear stress τ is divided by the dynamic pressure q) and is shown in Figure 8. The figure also indicates the skin friction coefficients for the laminar boundary layer ("Blasius") and the theoretical turbulent boundary layer ("Schulz-Grunov"). The actual measured data points (CPM) are located at clearly higher values of friction coefficients compared to the laminar case. The logarithmic regression $c_{f,CPM} = 0.976 \cdot (\log_{10} Re)^{-3.4966}$ was obtained from the measured data points and is plotted by the black line in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Turbulent calibration boundary layer

For the DSHF sensor calibration procedure the devices are calibrated w.r.t. their flow angle β and shear stress τ characteristic. An example of a calibration function is given in Figure 9. Each sensor element has its unique calibration surface. Every DSHF sensor features three calibration surfaces. In Figure 9 these surfaces are plotted w.r.t. the flow angle β and wall-shear stress τ . When the sensor is exposed to a boundary layer flow, one individual bridge voltage is measured for each surface hot film. In the calibration surface the measured bridge voltages appear as iso-lines. The measured state of the flow is found when the three iso-lines are projected in the β, τ plane. The projected curves intersect at one position β and τ and thereby indicate the measured state of the flow.

Figure 9: Calibration functions of one DSHF sensor; SHF – Surface Hot Film; $U_{br,i}$ – bridge voltage

To increase the measurement range of the DSHF sensors the calibration surfaces were extrapolated using Kings Law for every calibration angle.

Calibration procedure for high-speed experiments

For the calibration of the DSHF sensors at higher shear stress values a new calibration device was needed. A traversable impingement jet-nozzle was

Figure 10: calibration nozzle for large shear-stress values

designed and used to produce a wall-jet featuring sufficiently high amplitudes of the wall-shear stress. The calibration apparatus is illustrated Figure 10. The calibration nozzle generates an inclined impingement jet, that hits the surface under an impingement angle of 5° . The shear-stress profile that will be used for calibration depends on the distance to the outlet of the calibration nozzle. A nearly constant shear stress profile is crucial for a valid sensor calibration. In Figure 10 the obtained shear stress profile, measured at a distance of $d = 25$ mm downstream the outlet of the calibration nozzle is shown. In the centre of the curve a relatively wide range with constant shear stress is found. The sensors were placed within this range during calibration. The generated shear stress magnitude depends on the supply mass-flow of the device. This curve is also shown in Figure 10. The supply air mass-flow rate is controlled by a mass-flow control unit (Festo VPCF-6-L-8-G38-10). The obtained calibration function of the dSHF sensors equal the example shown in Figure 9. Optional a pre-conditioning unit can be attached that allows to control the jet temperature and the calibration shear stress magnitude independently. For the presented experiment the temperature characteristic of the sensors was calibrated separately in a climate chamber.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section results obtained from the two test rigs are presented. In the flat-plate configuration of the low-speed test section, the capability of the DSHF sensors to correctly measure the skin friction in a conventional turbulent boundary layer were examined. The application of the sensor in separated flow conditions was investigated in the

half-diffusor configuration of the low-speed test section. Additionally, experiments with pulsed blowing AFC were conducted to investigate the ability of the sensors to be used in dynamic flow conditions. In all experiments tripping of the boundary layer was installed at the leading edge of the test section. Furthermore, results from the highly three-dimensional test case are shown.

Low-speed test section in flat-plate configuration

Figure 11 shows the time-averaged shear stresses, as measured by the DSHF sensors w.r.t. the main-flow direction x and the span-wise direction y . Therefore, the test section was operated in the flat plate configuration (shown in Figure 1).

Figure 11: Wall-shear stress measured by the DSHF sensors on the flat plate configuration of the test section; CPM – Computational Preston tube Method; SG – Schulz-Grunov

The region of interest was located downstream the actuator orifices at a distance of $\Delta x=80\text{mm}$. The position of the coordinate system is indicated in Figure 3. After recording the data, the calibration procedure, as described above was applied. The main flow direction is well captured by the DSHF sensors, as indicated by the vector plot. The measured values range from $\tau=0.57\text{N/m}^2$ until $\tau=0.75\text{N/m}^2$. These shear stresses are within the calibrated range of the sensors. The span-wise averaging of the measured values was transferred into the friction coefficient c_f for comparing the data to the $c_f(Re)$ law from the calibration experiment. The logarithmic regression is also shown in the lower plot in Figure 11. The averaged data are plotted w.r.t. the local Reynolds number. In the

experiments the local Reynolds numbers were higher compared to the calibration experiments. Additionally, the $2 \cdot \sigma$ -error bars that resulted from the averaging are also shown in the plot. The black line (CPM fit) represents the regression curve as derived from the calibration experiment. Furthermore, the theoretical curves of the skin friction coefficient ($c_f = \tau/q_\infty$), as proposed for laminar flows (Blasius) and turbulent flows (Schulz-Grunov) are indicated. The dependency of the skin friction coefficient on the Reynolds number is well captured by the DSHF sensors. The data indicate decreasing skin-friction coefficients with increasing Reynolds number. The magnitudes of the measured skin frictions are located in-between the two theoretical boundary layer solutions. As it was also the case in the calibration experiments (Figure 8).

Low-speed test section in half diffusor configuration

When the test section was operated in the half-diffusor configuration, the flow was fully separated. The DSHF sensor positions were far downstream the separation point. This leads to very low local shear stresses. Figure 12 shows the shear-stress field as measured by the DSHF sensors. It is striking that the measured magnitudes of the shear stresses are lower compared to the case discussed above (attached boundary layer flow). The data show that the DSHF sensor has difficulties to measure the exact direction of the flow when the shear stress reaches values close to zero. By switching on the actuation the flow field is forced to re-attach and increased shear stresses result. Due to the unsteady actuation mechanism the local shear stress features periodic oscillations. The measured data with switched on actuation are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 12: Shear stress measured in the half diffusor configuration of the test section

Figure 13: Phase-resolved shear stress measured on the half-diffusor with AFC

For the plots the time-series data were averaged w.r.t. the working phase of the actuator. Therefore, the self-oscillating actuator from

Figure 3: Detailed setup of the test section was equipped with a dynamic pressure sensor that was installed in one of the feedback channels. The pressure sensor signal and the DSHF signals were recorded simultaneously. This allowed to phase-average the data in post-processing. Five different phase angles are shown in Figure 14. For phase angles ranging from $\phi = 0^\circ$ to $\phi = 180^\circ$ the outlet orifices 1 – 3 – 5 are active. For the rest of the phase angles the remaining orifices 2 – 4 – 6 are active. Downstream the outlet orifices of the actuator the injected high-speed jets form a Coandă wall jet. This leads to increased shear stresses, as measured for the phase-angles $\phi \leq 180^\circ$ at the position $y = 0$ mm. For higher phase-angles no fluid jet is injected from the outlet orifice at position $y = 0$ mm which leads to decreasing shear stress magnitudes at this position from there on. The region of increased shear stress is transported downstream for higher phase-angles, as depicted by the black circles. The green circles indicate the

trajectory of the high-speed pulsed jet injected from the actuator orifice, located at $y = 20$ mm. Due to three-dimensional effects in the flow the impact of the remaining four outlets are not seen in the phase-resolved data. In the outer region of the measurement domain, the flow is separated for all phase-angles ($x > 30$ mm and $y > 40$ mm). Here low shear-stress magnitudes were measured. Inside the Coandă jets maximum shear-stress magnitudes of $\tau = 3.6$ N/m² were measured by the DSHF sensors. This values are located outside the calibrated range of the sensors. Due to the extension of the calibration data, based on King's Law, the sensor is able to detect magnitudes and flow-angles located outside the calibrated range.

High-speed test section

An oil paint visualization was taken in advance to the DSHF measurements, in order to capture the flow structures. Figure 15 shows the results of the oil flow visualization for the cases of the actuated and the unactuated flow. In both cases the actuator orifices are shown at the position of $s/s_{max} = 0$. When the flow was not actuated the separation line

Figure 14: Comparison of the DSHF measurement with oil paint visualization

formed at the actuator orifices, due to the strong adverse pressure gradient. Downstream the separation line an asymmetric flow pattern forms. When the actuators were switched on (Figure 14; right hand side), two strong corner vortices form, due to the strong flow turning and the low aspect ratio of the ramp. One DSHF sensor was placed at the position marked in Figure 14. The measured bridge voltages were projected on the calibration surfaces, as also shown in the figure. For both cases the three curves intersect at one point. For the unactuated case, the measured shear stress equals $\tau = 0.03 \text{ N/m}^2$ and the detected flow angle was $\alpha = 270^\circ$. When the flow was actuated the detected shear stress increased, due to the re-attached flow. The measured value was $\tau = 6.5 \text{ N/m}^2$. In this case the detected direction of the wall-bounded stream line was $\alpha = 340^\circ$. The detected directions of the shear stresses are in agreement with the ones predicted by the oil-paint visualization.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the current paper a sensor architecture was proposed that uses three hot-film sensors arranged in an angular pattern to detect local wall-shear stress magnitude and also the direction of the shear-stress vector. A calibration procedure was discussed that allows to calibrate the characteristic of the sensor w.r.t. the shear stress and the flow angle. The sensor was tested in three different test configurations. In a low-speed turbulent flow the sensor was able to detect a plausible relation of the measured shear-stress magnitude to the Reynolds number. The measured data points were located close to the ones predicted by the law from in the calibration experiments. The sensor had difficulties predicting the shear stress direction in a separated flow regime, due to the low magnitudes of the shear stress. This could be improved by extending the calibration procedure by further points at low shear stress values. Furthermore, an active flow control case was investigated, where dynamic shear stress measurements were conducted on the half-diffuser with pulsed blowing actuation. It was feasible to detect the dynamic impact of the pulsed air jets to the magnitude of the shear stress. The direction was also measured correctly. Additionally, it was shown that the calibration function could be extrapolated using King's Law. In the third test the sensor was used in a highly three-dimensional flow regime. It was also shown that the direction of the shear stress was predicted correctly. The oil-paint visualization, used as reference technique, also indicated the measured directions of the wall-bounded stream lines. For the calibration of the shear stress sensors two devices were introduced. For the low-speed tests the sensors were calibrated in a flat-plate boundary layer, where the calibration shear stress was measured by a Preston tube. Each sensor was rotated around its axis to calibrate the characteristic

w.r.t. the flow angle. For calibrating higher values of shear stress an inclined impingement jet was proposed. The device allowed to calibrate the sensor for shear stresses up to $\tau = 50 \text{ N/m}^2$.

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